

Laparoscopic Management of a Symptomatic Giant Simple Hepatic Cyst Presenting with Chronic Right Hypochondrial Discomfort and Dyspepsia: A Case Report with Excellent Clinical Outcome

Min Nay Zar Wyke*¹, Soe Htut Aung², Aung Ko Ko Linn², Thant Lwyn San³, Khin Aung Htun⁴

¹Senior Consultant Surgeon, No. (1) Military Hospital (700-Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar.

¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0986-1047>

²Consultant Surgeon, No. (1) Military Hospital (700-Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar.

³Professor and Head of Department of Surgery, Defence Services Medical Academy, Yangon, Myanmar.

⁴Rector and Senior Consultant Surgeon, Defence Services Medical Academy, Yangon, Myanmar.

ABSTRACT

Background: Simple hepatic cysts are common benign liver lesions that are usually asymptomatic and incidentally detected. Giant hepatic cysts, however, may cause significant symptoms due to compression of adjacent organs, warranting surgical intervention. Minimally invasive approaches have become the standard of care for symptomatic simple hepatic cysts.

Case Presentation: A 55-year-old hypertensive woman presented with a one-year history of progressive right hypochondrial discomfort, abdominal distension, dyspepsia, and loss of appetite, without systemic symptoms or features of liver dysfunction. Imaging studies revealed a giant exophytic simple hepatic cyst arising from the posterior segments of the right lobe of the liver, measuring up to 15.5 cm with an estimated volume of 1276 mL. After preoperative optimization and cardiology consultation, laparoscopic cyst aspiration and wide deroofting were performed. Approximately 1400 mL of straw-colored fluid was aspirated. Histopathology confirmed a simple hepatic cyst. The postoperative course was uneventful, with complete symptomatic relief and no evidence of recurrence on follow-up.

Conclusion: Laparoscopic deroofting is a safe, effective, and minimally invasive treatment for symptomatic giant simple hepatic cysts, providing excellent clinical outcomes with low morbidity.

KEYWORDS: Simple hepatic cyst, giant cyst, laparoscopic cyst aspiration, laparoscopic deroofting, minimally invasive surgery, symptomatic, cytology, histopathology, outcome.

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INTRODUCTION

Simple hepatic cysts are benign, fluid-filled lesions of the liver, most often congenital in origin and lined by cuboidal epithelium. They are thought to arise from aberrant bile duct development during embryogenesis and are frequently detected incidentally during imaging performed for unrelated indications. The prevalence of simple hepatic cysts increases with age and is reported to range from 2% to 18% in the general population, depending on the diagnostic modality used (1,2). Most hepatic cysts remain

asymptomatic throughout life and require no intervention (2).

Despite their benign nature, a subset of hepatic cysts may enlarge progressively and become symptomatic. Giant hepatic cysts, generally defined as cysts larger than 10 cm in diameter, can exert a mass effect on surrounding organs, including the stomach, duodenum, colon, diaphragm, and kidney. This mass effect may result in abdominal distension, discomfort, pain, dyspepsia, early satiety, nausea, or even respiratory symptoms (2,3). Rarely, complications such as

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intracystic hemorrhage, infection, rupture, or biliary obstruction may occur (3).

The differential diagnosis of a large hepatic cyst includes hydatid disease, biliary cystadenoma or cystadenocarcinoma, abscess, necrotic tumor, and polycystic liver disease. Accurate diagnosis is therefore critical, as management strategies vary significantly depending on the underlying pathology. Ultrasonography and contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CECT) play a central role in characterizing cyst morphology, wall thickness, internal septations, calcifications, and solid components, which help distinguish simple cysts from more complex lesions (2,6).

Management of hepatic cysts is guided primarily by symptomatology rather than size alone. Asymptomatic cysts, even if large, may be managed conservatively with observation. In contrast, symptomatic cysts usually require intervention. Treatment options include percutaneous aspiration with or without sclerotherapy, open surgical deroofing, cyst excision, hepatic resection, and laparoscopic deroofing (3,4). Percutaneous aspiration alone is associated with a high recurrence rate, whereas sclerotherapy may reduce recurrence but carries risks of bile duct injury and chemical peritonitis (4,5).

With advances in minimally invasive surgery, laparoscopic deroofing has become the preferred treatment for symptomatic simple hepatic cysts. This approach allows wide excision of the cyst wall, effective decompression, and durable symptom relief while minimizing surgical trauma, postoperative pain, and hospital stay (3,5). Laparoscopic management has been shown to be safe and effective, with low recurrence rates when adequate cyst wall excision is achieved (5,7).

This case report presents a 55-year-old woman with a giant symptomatic simple hepatic cyst of the right lobe, successfully treated with laparoscopic aspiration and deroofing. The case highlights the importance of comprehensive preoperative evaluation, careful surgical technique, and postoperative follow-up in achieving optimal outcomes.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 55-year-old woman presented to the surgical outpatient department with complaints of progressive abdominal distension, dull aching pain, and a sense of discomfort in the right hypochondrial region for approximately one year. The symptoms were insidious in onset and gradually progressive. She also reported dyspepsia and loss of appetite over the same duration. There was no history of weight loss, nausea, vomiting, fever, jaundice, or change in bowel habits. The patient denied any history of abdominal trauma or previous abdominal surgery.

Her past medical history was significant for hypertension, with recorded maximum blood pressure readings up to 160/100 mmHg. She was on regular antihypertensive

medication with good compliance. There was no history of diabetes mellitus, chronic liver disease, tuberculosis, or malignancy. She had no known drug allergies and no significant family history of liver disease.

On general examination, the patient was conscious and hemodynamically stable. She was well nourished, with no pallor, jaundice, cyanosis, clubbing, or peripheral edema. Blood pressure was 150/90 mmHg, and pulse rate was 86 beats per minute with a regular rhythm. Respiratory rate and body temperature were normal, and oxygen saturation was normal on room air. Abdominal examination showed mild distension with visible fullness and a mildly tender palpable bulge in the right hypochondrial region. The abdomen was soft, with no guarding, rigidity, rebound tenderness, or ascites. Bowel sounds were normal. Other system examinations were unremarkable.

Laboratory investigations revealed normal hematological, renal, hepatic, and coagulation parameters, including hemoglobin of 13.6 g/dL, white blood cell count of $6.13 \times 10^9/L$, platelet count of $306 \times 10^9/L$, serum creatinine of 43.8 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, C-reactive protein of 0.1 mg/L, total bilirubin of 9.9 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, normal liver enzymes, prothrombin time of 12.1 seconds, and INR of 1.05. Viral serology for hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and retroviral infection was non-reactive. Cardiac evaluation demonstrated normal sinus rhythm on electrocardiography. Echocardiography showed normal cardiac chambers and valves with preserved left ventricular systolic function and an ejection fraction of 65%. Chest radiography revealed mild cardiomegaly without pulmonary pathology (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Chest X-ray showing mild cardiomegaly and normal lung parenchyma.

Abdominal ultrasonography demonstrated a large, well-defined anechoic cyst in the right lobe of the liver measuring $10.2 \times 12.1 \times 13.3$ cm, consistent with a simple hepatic cyst, without internal septations or solid components (Figure 2 & 3).

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Figure 2. Ultrasound (abdomen) showing a giant simple hepatic cyst in the right lobe of the liver.

Figure 3. Ultrasound (abdomen) showing a large simple hepatic cyst in the right lobe of the liver measuring approximately 10.2 × 12.1 × 13.3 cm.

Contrast-enhanced CT confirmed a giant exophytic simple hepatic cyst arising from the posterior segments of the right lobe (Figure 4), measuring 10.7 × 14.8 × 15.5 cm with an estimated volume of 1276 mL, thin walls, and homogeneous low attenuation (approximately 6 HU). The cyst caused anterior displacement of the right hepatic lobe and anteromedial displacement of the right kidney (Figure 5 & 6). Additional small simple hepatic cysts were noted in segments III and V, with no evidence of ascites or biliary dilatation.

Figure 4. Axial contrast-enhanced CT image showing a giant exophytic simple hepatic cyst in the right lobe of the liver measuring 10.7 × 14.8 × 15.5 cm, with thin walls and homogeneous low-attenuation fluid content.

Figure 5. Coronal CECT image showing a giant right lobe hepatic cyst (10.7 × 14.8 × 15.5 cm) with simple fluid content and mass effect on the liver and right kidney.

Figure 6. Sagittal CECT image showing a giant right lobe hepatic cyst (10.7 × 14.8 × 15.5 cm) with simple fluid content and mass effect on the liver and right kidney.

Given the patient's persistent symptoms, large cyst size, and imaging features consistent with a simple hepatic cyst, surgical intervention was planned. After optimization of blood pressure and consultation with a cardiologist, the patient was scheduled for elective laparoscopic management.

Figure 7. Intraoperative laparoscopic view showing a giant bulging hepatic cyst occupying the right lobe of the liver.

Intraoperatively, laparoscopic exploration revealed a large bulging cyst occupying the right lobe of the liver, causing downward displacement of the liver (Figure 7). There were no ascites or evidence of peritoneal disease. Laparoscopic aspiration yielded approximately 1400 mL of clear, straw-coloured fluid (Figure 8 & 9). Following decompression, wide deroofing of the cyst wall was performed using an advanced energy device (Karl Storz Lotus) (Figure 10). A

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drainage tube was placed at the deroofing site (Figure 11 & 12). The excised cyst wall was submitted for histopathological examination (Figure 13), and the aspirated cyst fluid was sent for routine examination and cytological analysis.

Figure 8. Laparoscopic view showing needle aspiration of the hepatic cyst with evacuation of clear straw-coloured fluid.

Figure 9. Aspirated cystic fluid measuring approximately 1400 mL of clear, straw-coloured fluid.

Figure 10. Intraoperative views of laparoscopic deroofing of the hepatic cyst using a Karl Storz Lotus energy device.

Figure 11. Laparoscopic view showing insertion of a drainage tube at the site of cyst deroofing.

Figure 12. Postoperative abdominal view of laparoscopic port sites with abdominal drain.

The postoperative course was uneventful. On the first postoperative day, drain output was approximately 400 mL and gradually decreased over subsequent days. The patient tolerated a semisolid diet on the first postoperative day, progressing to a full diet without difficulty. The drain was removed on the fourth postoperative day when output decreased to 20 mL. She was discharged on the fifth postoperative day in good condition.

Figure 13. Gross specimen of the excised hepatic cyst wall following laparoscopic deroofing.

Cytological analysis of the aspirated cyst fluid showed benign cystic fluid with no malignant cells (Figure 14). Routine examination revealed no acid-fast bacilli on Ziehl–Neelsen staining, no microorganisms on Gram staining, and no red blood cells on Leishman staining, with only scattered lymphocytes and neutrophils observed. Histopathological examination of the cyst wall confirmed a simple hepatic cyst without features of malignancy (Figure 15).

Figure 14. Cytological examination of aspirated hepatic cyst fluid showing benign cytology.

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Figure 15. Histopathological examination of the excised cyst wall showing features of a simple hepatic cyst.

Follow-up ultrasonography demonstrated no residual cyst, no free fluid, and no biloma formation. At follow-up visits at one week, two weeks, and one month postoperatively, the patient reported complete resolution of abdominal discomfort, good appetite, and return to normal daily activities.

DISCUSSION

Simple hepatic cysts are the most common non-parasitic cystic lesions of the liver and are usually discovered incidentally (1,2). They are more frequently observed in women and tend to increase in size with age (2). Although most remain asymptomatic, large cysts may become clinically significant due to mass effect on adjacent organs, as demonstrated in the present case (3).

The clinical presentation of symptomatic hepatic cysts is often nonspecific, including abdominal pain, fullness, distension, dyspepsia, and early satiety (2,3). In this patient, chronic right hypochondrial discomfort and dyspepsia were the predominant symptoms, which significantly affected her quality of life despite the absence of systemic or constitutional features.

Accurate diagnosis is essential to differentiate simple hepatic cysts from other cystic liver lesions with malignant potential. Imaging plays a pivotal role in this differentiation. Ultrasonography typically shows a well-defined anechoic lesion with posterior acoustic enhancement, while CECT demonstrates a thin-walled, non-enhancing cyst with homogeneous low attenuation (6). The absence of septations, mural nodules, or wall thickening strongly favors a diagnosis of a simple cyst (6,7).

Management strategies for hepatic cysts depend primarily on symptomatology. Asymptomatic cysts do not require treatment, whereas symptomatic cysts warrant intervention (3,4). Percutaneous aspiration alone has a high recurrence rate, often exceeding 80%, due to continued secretion by the cyst epithelium. The addition of sclerotherapy reduces

recurrence but carries risks, including bile duct injury and chemical peritonitis (4,5).

Surgical options include open or laparoscopic deroofting, cyst excision, and hepatic resection (3,4). Open surgery is associated with increased postoperative pain, longer hospital stay, and higher morbidity. Laparoscopic deroofting has emerged as the preferred approach due to its minimally invasive nature, reduced morbidity, and excellent symptom control (3,5).

In the present case, laparoscopic deroofting was chosen because of the cyst's large size, exophytic location, and benign imaging features. The use of an advanced energy device facilitated precise and hemostatic excision of the cyst wall. Adequate deroofting is crucial to prevent recurrence by eliminating the secretory epithelium and allowing continuous drainage into the peritoneal cavity (5,7).

The placement of a drain remains a topic of debate (5). In this case, a drain was placed to monitor postoperative output and detect potential bile leakage. The gradual reduction in drain output and absence of bile suggested an uncomplicated postoperative course, supporting early drain removal.

Histopathological confirmation is essential to exclude rare differential diagnoses such as biliary cystadenoma or cystadenocarcinoma (2,6). In this patient, both cytology and histology confirmed the benign nature of the lesion, and no further treatment was required.

Postoperative outcomes following laparoscopic deroofting are generally excellent, with high rates of symptom resolution and low recurrence rates (5,7). Early mobilization, rapid resumption of oral intake, and short hospital stay are additional advantages. The present case demonstrated complete symptomatic relief and uneventful recovery.

Long-term follow-up is recommended to detect recurrence, particularly in patients with multiple cysts (7). In this case, short-term follow-up showed no evidence of recurrence, biloma, or other complications, and the patient returned to normal daily activities with improved quality of life.

CONCLUSION

Symptomatic giant simple hepatic cysts, although benign, can significantly impair quality of life due to mass effect on surrounding structures. Accurate radiological diagnosis is essential to exclude malignant or parasitic cystic liver diseases. Laparoscopic aspiration with wide deroofting provides definitive management and offers a safe, effective, and minimally invasive treatment with excellent clinical outcomes. This case supports laparoscopic deroofting as the preferred management strategy for appropriately selected patients with symptomatic giant simple hepatic cysts.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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